

Perception of Teachers and Students Towards Constructivist Approach of Teaching: A Study with Special Reference to Vivekananda Kendriya Vidyalayas

Pratima das
Research Scholar

&
Dr. Alaka Das
Associate Professor

Kumar Bhaskar Varma Sanskrit & Ancient Studies University, Nalbari

Abstract of the Study

Swami Vivekananda's philosophy of education is a harmonious blend of ancient Indian wisdom and modern constructivist principles. His 'Man Making Education' emphasized discussions, self-study, and travel that mirror constructivist approaches of learning, fostering independent, ethical, and socially-conscious individuals. This educational framework draws from India's rich traditions contributes significantly to the global understanding of constructivism. Vivekananda Kendriya Vidyalayas of Assam cherish these ideals and principles of education in the schools while imparting education. It is often stated that one of the limitations of science education is the overdependency of traditional methods of teaching science and for effective science learning, use of innovative pedagogies is of utmost need. In this paper, an attempt has been made to know the perception of the Science teachers and students towards constructivist approach of learning while teaching science using descriptive approach of research. Required data were collected from randomly selected sample groups of (50) science teachers and 140 students studying at Vivekananda Kendriya Vidyalayas through two adapted tools of assessing perception towards constructivist approach of teaching. Findings of the study reflect positive and notable perception of the actual constructivist classroom practices teaching in science teaching.

Keywords: Perception, Vivekananda, Constructivism, Vivekananda Kendriya Vidyalas

Introduction

Swami Vivekananda's educational philosophy, deeply rooted in the ancient Indian ethos, aligns closely with the principles of constructivism. He envisioned education as a holistic process that fosters the complete development of an individual. His emphasis on 'man-making education' reflects the constructivist idea of learning as an active, self-driven process. Vivekananda believed in education that cultivates concentration, encourages self-learning, and promotes interactive methods like discussion and question-answer sessions. Vivekananda's approach resonates with the modern constructivist perspective, which values the learner's active role in making sense of their experiences to build knowledge. His educational thought practices encourage learners to become self-reliant, morally upright, and socially responsible individuals, capable of contributing to society's progress. This vision of education not only nurtures the roots of constructivism but also enriches it with the profound wisdom of India's ancient traditions.

Constructivism

Constructivism as constructs of epistemological approach of knowledge as well as learning theory in the 21st century attempts to explain how we acquire and construct our knowledge in our own way. Constructivism holds that knowledge is subjective, situational and inherently partial. The constructivist approach to teaching, rooted in Piaget's theory, emphasizes active learning where students build their own understanding and knowledge, rather than just absorbing information from a teacher. Constructivism says that people make or build their new meanings or knowledge by connecting what they already have in their minds and what they experience with the things, happenings, and actions that they encounter. In the similar note, Vivekananda attempts to interpret education. Lev Vygotsky, a prominent figure in the constructivist domain, is renowned for his work on social constructivism. Both Piaget and Vygotsky emphasized that learning occurs during observations and active engagement in various activities. It challenges the notion that learners passively receive knowledge from external sources. Instead, learners actively construct understanding based on their previous personal experiences. In this context, the teacher's role has transformed from merely imparting information to creating meaningful learning opportunities. This shift significantly impacts how teachers approach their teaching methods through five "E"s- Engage, Explore,

Explain, Elaborate, and Evaluation. In this context, the study attempts to explore the science teacher's perception towards constructivists approach of teaching.

Swami Vivekananda and Constructivism

For Vivekananda, education is man-making through acquiring knowledge, formation of character, development of social traits. Swami Vivekananda's philosophy of education emphasizes the concept of self-manifestation. He believed that education is not just the acquisition of external knowledge, but a process of bringing forth the inherent wisdom within an individual. According to him, every person possesses an innate perfection and the role of education is to remove the obstacles that prevent this perfection from shining forth. Vivekananda's view aligns with the idea of constructivist self-education, that true education is about nurturing the whole individual, fostering character development, and encouraging the expression of one's inner potential.

Constructivism and Science Education

From a constructivist viewpoint, science is viewed not as a quest for absolute truth but rather as a method to help us understand our surroundings. Teaching science through this lens transforms it into a dynamic and collaborative endeavour of interpreting experiences, much like how scientists operate (Driver, R.1989). This contrasts with traditional "school science," which is often more passive. The push for science education reform emphasizes active student participation—encouraging "hands-on, minds-on" learning. Adopting constructivism as a guiding principle can be instrumental in achieving this progressive and engaging approach to science education. Teachers, guided by a constructivist perspective, can better understand students' existing knowledge and how they make sense of the world. This awareness helps bridge the gap between scientific explanations and students' real-world understanding. Exploring students' perception about constructivist approach of learning has therefore implications in adopting constructivist approach of teaching in science classroom. The problem of the study reads as follows-

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Objectives of the Study

1. To know Vivekananda's perspective on education and constructivism
2. To study the perception of the science teachers towards constructivist approach of teaching
3. To study the perception of students towards constructivist approach of teaching practices
4. To find out the significance of difference in level of attitude towards constructivist approach of teaching between boys and girls' students

Significance of the study

The current educational trend is to adopt a constructivist approach to address the evolving challenges within the educational systems. This approach is supported by the National Educational Policy 2020, that advocates for a learning experience that is experiential, enjoyable, and centered around the learner. Learning is seen as a result of one's actions and reflections, leading to a deeper connection with the subject matter and a lasting comprehension. Attitudes play a crucial role as they influence behaviour. Teachers with a positive attitude towards the constructivist approach are likely to implement it effectively in the classroom, whereas those with a negative attitude may require more preparation for its application. The study aims to reveal the perceptions of teachers towards the constructivist method of teaching, which is pivotal for its successful integration into educational practice. Since teachers' views on constructivism can differ based on their expertise and the subjects they teach, the study aims to gather insights from science teachers at Vivekananda Kendriya Vidyalayas—schools that are influenced by Vivekananda's holistic educational philosophy. The anticipated outcome of the study is expected to highlight how do the science teachers perceive and practice constructivist approach of teaching in their classrooms.

Related Literature Review

Studies on teachers perception towards constructivist approach has been studied by Mondal (2014) and found male teachers having more constructivist approach in their teaching as compared to female teachers. Kumar (2015) studied Swami Vivekananda's Educational

thoughts in present context in terms of Vedanta. Ujjwal Paul (2018) found that in west Bengal, constructivist approach of entire education system specially in science education are yet to take firm position (attitude) for translating constructivist vision into practice (action) in real classroom situation. Das (2020) in his study focussed on how man making education helps for promoting education. Badsah (2020) discussed about Vivekananda thought on educational system and the teacher. Roy (2021) discussed Vivekananda's aims of education, teaching method, curriculum, schools and teachers in the context of the present social system. Soy (2023) analysed NEP 2020 in the Light of Swami Vivekananda's Educational Philosophy. From the reviews it has been observed that studies on perception toward constructivist approach of teaching of teachers and students are not that much available and particularly on science teachers of Vivekananda Kendriya Vidyalayas. Therefore, study attempted to explore the perception of the science teachers and students as well on constructivist approach of teaching practices.

Methods and Tools

To know the science teachers and students' perspective towards constructivist approach of teaching in classroom, descriptive research approach has been adopted. Primary data have been collected through two adapted version of questionnaires that were basically developed by Ahmedi V., Kurshumlija, A., & Ismajli, H. (2003), both for teachers and students. Sample of the study consists of 50 teachers and 140 students selected randomly from 4 Vivekananda Kendriya Vidyalas of Assam.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

Objective No 1: Vivekananda on Education and constructivism

Vivekananda's educational methods draw from ancient Indian traditions remain highly relevant. He advocated for meditation and yoga as means to enhance mental concentration and readiness for learning. Differentiating literacy with education Swamiji further elaborated "Education is not filling the mind with a lot of facts. Perfecting the instrument and getting complete mastery of my own mind is the ideal of education." constructivists approach of teaching in Vivekananda's man making education may be observed in following aspects. Self-Education- Emphasizing self-education, he believed that true learning cannot be forced, aligning closely with the constructivist approach where learners actively construct their own understanding.

Manifestation of innate perfection - Swami Vivekananda's educational philosophy centres on the idea that true education is the manifestation of innate perfection within individuals. He viewed the mind of a child as a blank slate, with teachers responsible for shaping their character and intellect.

Creative Learning Process-Vivekananda championed a creative learning process, where education is not just about absorbing information but about drawing out ideas and fostering creativity.

Knowledge through practical experiences- Vivekananda believed that knowledge grows when linked to practical experiences and that intelligence is cultivated through an intrinsic desire for learning.

Teacher as Facilitator-Teachers, in his view, are facilitators who guide students towards self-realization and encourage them to question, think critically, and construct new knowledge. He advocated for a constructivist approach, emphasizing that focusing solely on results limits creativity. Instead, teachers should inspire students to be innovative, ensuring their growth into successful, creative individuals.

Despite 150 years of gap, Swami Vivekananda's philosophy of education remains relevant in present time education, reflecting the timeless value of his approach to teaching and learning that have immense implication in different aspects of education. The enduring originality of thought of Vivekananda on 'Man Making Education through constructivist approach' is a source of inspiration.

Objective 2-Secondary School teacher's Perception Towards Constructivist Approach of Teaching

Table 1: Secondary School teacher's Perception Towards Constructivist Approach of Teaching
N=50

Sl No	Statements In teaching, you as teacher-	Yes (%)	Not sure(%)	No (%)
1	Wish to implement the constructivist approach in your classroom	37 (74)	6 (12)	7 (14)
2	Plan the lessons as per the needs of the students	36 (72)	8 (16)	6 (12)
3	New concept is introduced through connecting student's life experiences	38 (76)	5 (10)	7 (14)
4	While teaching, encourage multiple approach of questioning	37 (74)	8 (16)	5 (10)
5	In answering questions, group collaboration among the students is encouraged	37 (74)	6 (12)	7 (14)

6	Prepare lessons keeping in view the individual difference of the students	36 (72)	8 (16)	6 (12)
7	During group activity, students are encouraged to share and compare their ideas	32 (64)	10 (20)	8 (16)
8	Instruction is designed with consideration for the unique interest of each learner	40 (80)	1 (2)	9 (18)
9	Students are taught to take responsibility of own learning through exploration	35 (70)	4 (8)	11 (22)
10	Encourage students to develop their own ideas and solutions	40 (80)	1 (2)	9 (18)
11	Assess students' progress continuously using group assessments	38 (76)	6 (12)	6 (12)
12	Self-evaluation remains a constituent part of student evaluation	39 (78)	1 (2)	10 (20)
13	Adopt innovative strategy to engage students in self-learning and construct knowledge	33 (66)	9 (18)	8 (16)
14	Use digital tools for interactive teaching in the classrooms	40 (80)	0	10 (20)
15	Regularly revisit the topic till the students achieve mastery	39 (78)	3 (6)	8 (16)
16	Constructivist approach of teaching is problematic for teachers	31 (62)	4 (8)	15 (3)
17	Course completion is not possible in Constructivist approach of teaching	39 (78)	0	11 (22)
18	Teacher is not able to pay equal attention to each learner	33 (66)	6 (12)	11 (22)
19	Group projects make it hard to finish the syllabus	38 (76)	4 (8)	8 (16)
20	Teachers providing learning autonomy discourages the students	36 (72)	3 (6)	11 (22)

From the Table 1 it is found that the constructivist approach in education, which emphasizes active learning practices and student engagement through practical activities and teamwork, is supported by a majority of teachers. According to the data, 74% of teachers are in favour of implementing this approach and tailoring lessons to meet the diverse needs and learning styles of students. A similar percentage agrees that connecting new concepts to students' real-life experiences enhances understanding. Teachers also recognize the importance of encouraging students to ask questions and work collaboratively, with 72% to 80% agreeing on these methods. While the approach is generally viewed positively, there are concerns about its practicality, such as the difficulty in covering the entire syllabus (78%) and giving equal attention to all students (66%). Despite these challenges, the consensus is that with proper understanding and application, the constructivist approach can significantly benefit learners.

Table 2: Secondary School teacher's Perception Towards Constructivist Approach of Teaching N=50

Level of Perception	Number of Teachers	Mean score	S D
Low	4	47.94	6.42
Average	22		
High	24		

From the Table No 2, The data reveals the mean perception score of the teachers is 47.94 with a deviation of 6.42. It also reflects that teachers' attitudes towards the constructivist teaching approach vary, with scores ranging from 59 to 30. A small group of 4 teachers falls into the low perception category, 22 teachers are in the average range, and the largest group, consisting of 24 teachers, exhibits a high level of perception. This distribution suggests that the majority of teachers view constructivist teaching methods positively. This finding supports previous studies by Uredi (2013), Hursen and Soykara (2012), and Guha and Paul (2014), which also concluded that the predominant sentiment among teachers is favorable towards the adoption of constructivist teaching methods.

Objective No 3-Student's Perception Towards Constructivist Approach of Teaching

Table 3: Student's Perception Towards Constructivist Approach of Teaching N=140

Sl NO	Statements	Yes (%)	Not sure (%)	N0 (%)
1	In Classroom learning, you as learner - Collaborate with peers in group activities and projects	80 (57)	20(14)	40(28)
2	Feel free to raise questions while experiencing learning	90(64)	23(16)	27(19)
3	Apart from teacher, share curiosity and doubts with peers about the lessons	93(66)	32(22)	15(10)
4	Express opinions freely though it contradicts with class point of view	94(67)	35(25)	11(7)
5	Teacher praises me while I explore unique thoughts by myself	96(68)	18(12)	26(18)
6	Teacher continuously assesses us in group activities	97(69)	31(22)	12(8)
7	Teachers encourages us to plan the project to be presented by ourselves	99(70)	25(17)	16(11)

8	Relating day to day life experiences help in understanding science	113(80)	11(7)	16(11)
9	Used to work in group for solution of problems in different subjects	102(72)	18(12)	20(14)
10	Teachers provide opportunity to correct mistakes	89(63)	35(25)	16(11)
11	At the end of lessons, evaluate achievement by myself	92(65)	31(22)	17(12)
12	Try to relate science experience with practical life situations	105(75)	19(13)	16(11)

Data of Table No 3 reflects a positive student response to the constructivist approach, with over half expressing interest in peer collaboration and group work, which is seen as a driver of innovation and productivity. A majority of students value the encouragement of questions and the sharing of doubts during lessons, as it deepens understanding and fosters a sense of community. The freedom to voice differing opinions is also appreciated, as it enhances critical thinking and inclusivity. Teachers' support is crucial for nurturing students' creativity and confidence, with continuous assessment during group activities being recognized for its role in monitoring progress. Students also embrace the responsibility of planning project presentations, which promotes autonomy. Linking everyday experiences with scientific concepts is highly regarded for making learning more relatable and understandable. Group problem-solving is favoured for its ability to bring diverse insights and develop well-rounded solutions. Opportunities to rectify errors are seen as essential for a growth mindset, while self-assessment at the end of lessons is valued for promoting self-reflection and responsibility. Overall, students acknowledge the importance of applying scientific knowledge to practical situations, enhancing their ability to use what they learn in real-life scenarios.

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Table 4: Level of Perception of the Students towards Constructivist approach of Teaching

N=140

Level of Perception	Number of students	Mean score	S D
Low (15-24)	25	32.9	4.27
Average (25-34)	65		
High (35-44)	50		

Table 4 reveals that student's perception towards constructivists approach of teaching range from (15-44). In low level there are 25 students, while in high level 55 students and highest students fell into average category. Students' perception towards constructivists approach of teaching in terms of mean score of (32.9) with a standard deviation of 4.27 which is above average score. It indicates student's highly favourable attitude towards constructivists approach of teaching practices.

Table 5: Significance of difference in mean perception towards constructivists approach of teaching between boys and girl's student N=140

Category	Category	Number of students	Mean score	S D	t'	Level of Significance
Sex	Boys	65	31.10	4.90	7.12	Not significant
	Girls	75	34.45	2.86		

From the table No 5, it has been observed that, the mean perception score towards constructivist approach of teaching of the boys is 31.10 with a standard deviation of 4.90 and that of girls' students is 34.45 with standard deviation of 2.86, and the mean scores difference of both boys and girl students is not statistically significant. However, in comparison to girl students, boys have a more favourable attitude towards constructivist approach of teaching though the difference is minimum.

Educational implication of the study

The study emphasizes the importance of the constructivist approach in modern education, particularly in science. It explores the dynamics of teacher self-presentation, student engagement, and the interaction between the two in the classroom. Embracing diverse student responses and effective lesson planning are crucial for implementing constructivism. Starting with small changes and gradually moving from traditional methods to a more innovative

environment can aid in meeting the National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 goals. Despite the challenges, increased awareness and understanding of constructivism are expected to foster a positive attitude among students and teachers, leading to its successful application in actual classroom settings. More information on constructivism can lead to a shift in attitudes and teaching practices.

Suggestion and Conclusion

constructivist approach in teaching, emphasizes the shift from traditional teacher-led instruction to a student-centered model. This approach nurtures an active learning environment where students can relate lessons to real-life situations, collaborate, and undertake group projects. The success of this method however depend on training of both new and experienced teachers, focusing on constructivist strategies and their impact on secondary education. Teachers' positive perceptions of constructivist teaching methods suggest its effective implementation and potential areas for enhancement. Ultimately, the study underscores the significance of constructivist teaching for the advancement of the education system, recommending the adoption of constructivist methods, policies, and programs to foster a positive mindset in teachers. This, in turn, will enable them to create a conducive learning environment that significantly benefits students.

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